

VIEWPOINT

Between exclusionary nationalism and urban citizenship in East Jerusalem/ al-Quds

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In recent years, Israel has witnessed a wave of heightened nationalism. Although nationalism is not new at all in this part of the world—quite the contrary—Israel's acting Prime Minister Netanyahu and his government are today part of an international alliance of leaders (including Donald Trump, Jair Bolsonaro, Viktor Orbán, and Narendra Modi) promoting neo-nationalism and right-wing populism. Notwithstanding the significant global aspects of neo-nationalist phenomenon, as described by de Souza (2020), Koch and Vora (2020) and Yiftachel and Rokem (2020), this commentary focuses on nationalism's localized manifestations in Jerusalem/al-Quds, highlighting the way local dynamics complicate and subvert nationalism's powerful influence.

In Jerusalem/al-Quds, a city known for its violent history and contested sovereignty, the national scale has always been extremely present in everyday life, rendering the city an embodiment of nationalist and colonial logics (Shlomo 2017; Yiftachel 2016). However, I would like to suggest a counter-logic to the top-down form of exclusionary nationalist citizenship, one that attempts to consolidate a more inclusive urban citizenship 'from below.' In this sense, urban politics are not just a reflection of the national sphere writ small; rather, these politics point to the contradictions and 'cracks' that might arise between national ideology and more local action (see Braier 2013). Jerusalem is hence today equally a site of fierce ethnonationalist conflict and of resistance to ethnonationalism—a tension that play out through different grassroots organizations and their activities around the city. To be sure, this urban citizenship is delicate and fragile and still in the making; it is not yet a feasible alternative to national citizenship or a remedy for political oppressions. Yet, in a

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context of resurgent nationalism, it might point the way to a more hopeful geopolitics. Or, it may simply signal a shift from the highly ideological to the pragmatic. Either way, localized geographies of citizenship should not be overlooked.

Jerusalem has been the epicentre of nationalist projects executed by the Israeli government, as well as a site of protest by competing Palestinian nationalist agendas. The asymmetry of relationships between Palestinians and Israelis is especially evident in East Jerusalem, which is the common, although geographically inaccurate, name for Jerusalem's Palestinian neighbourhoods. Most Palestinians in Jerusalem (who constitute 38 percent of the population) are residents and not citizens of Israel. They must continuously prove that they live in Jerusalem, and that Jerusalem is their “center of life,” or they risk losing their already precarious status as permanent residents. For the majority who do not have any other national citizenship, this outcome would result in a stateless status (see Koch and Vora 2020 for further analysis of the use of the law to exclude minorities in the context of ethnonationalism). Their continued existence in a gray space in which they are neither fully included nor excluded from Israel (Avni and Yiftachel 2014) subjects many Palestinians to threats of house demolitions, violence, and permanent insecurity. Palestinians in East Jerusalem are routinely reminded of the precariousness of their status. Sports tournaments in Beit Safafa and other Palestinian neighbourhoods, for instance, are regularly shut down by Israeli police on the pretext that they are a ‘national’ political activity. Indeed, many cultural events and festivals that are civic and ‘ordinary’ in nature and not directly related to formal, national-level politics are also hindered by the Israeli police or army.

As the nationalist rhetoric around Jerusalem has intensified in recent years, so has the impact of this rhetoric on the ground. While the government approved a five-year plan to reduce socio-economic gaps in East Jerusalem, critiques argue that its implementation intensifies Israel’s presence there—for instance, by requiring Palestinian schools to adopt the Israeli curriculum as a condition for funding. Other plans are even blunter in their symbolic aspirations, such as the controversial Mount Zion cable car to the Western Wall, which is planned to bypass Palestinian areas and strengthen tourism to Jerusalem's Jewish landmarks (Kimmelman 2019). In terms of housing, while the municipality has promoted some new small-scale master

plans in East Jerusalem, these are negligible in scope and often fail to get approval from the District and State level.

Yet while nationalist, militaristic, colonial, and religious forces continue to dominate East Jerusalem, they are not the only ones shaping everyday life there. Neo-nationalism is complicated by processes operating at other scales, whether through international law, as noted by Koch and Vora (2020), or, in this case, through urban politics. Since the construction of the Separation Wall in the early 2000s, Palestinian neighbourhoods in Jerusalem have been cut off from the West Bank; as a result, and somewhat ironically, these neighborhoods have now become more integrated into West Jerusalem. While the city is still highly segregated along ethnic and religious lines, Palestinians and Israelis have increasingly encountered one another in shops, parks, and public transportation, albeit still in the context of asymmetric power-relations and economic dependency (Shtern 2016; Greenberg Raanan and Avni 2020). This relatively new set of circumstances has, to some extent, brought a growing salience to the 'urban' over the 'national', even if only in a very pragmatic sense. Thus, today, we see more interaction between East and West Jerusalem, whether through grassroots initiatives or more institutional channels in the areas of education, urban planning, culture, and community development (Shlomo 2017).

One arena in which this interaction has taken place is the Community Council (CC). There are 30 councils in Jerusalem, of which only seven are in East Jerusalem. The CCs all around the city are an intermediary governance structure that is supposed to represent residents in different matters and to provide various services in the areas of education, culture, sports, and physical planning. CCs are positioned in the unenviable position of mediating between the residents and the municipality (Rosen and Avni 2019). This position is particularly contentious in East Jerusalem. Even though East-Jerusalemites can vote for the municipal council, most of them boycott these elections because the municipality is perceived to be part of the so-called "normalization" of the occupation. The CCs, which are partly financed by the municipality (the other part is funded by the Israel Association of Community Centers), – are not readily accepted among the Palestinian public and are viewed by many as working against the Palestinian national struggle.

However, the CCs also provide much-needed services and a platform for community engagement in neighbourhoods deprived of even basic amenities. In research conducted with colleagues from the Hebrew University of Jerusalem, we found that despite the CC's contested status, they still serve important functions in the community, and in some cases, manage to rise above their problematic image and build trust and legitimacy among residents. Some have managed to promote small-scale master plans while others have coordinated aid during the Covid-19 crisis or have organized neighbourhood clean-ups. The findings reveal the tensions between the national scale with which the CCs are associated (i.e. Israeli political domination and occupation) and the more everyday urban needs they seek to address. When successful, they bring tangible benefits to marginalized and deprived neighbourhoods in the form of education, culture, professional development, and leadership training.

Beyond the CCs, it is important to note other arenas through which Palestinians claim their right to the city, both via shared projects with Israelis and independently. These include, but are not limited to, initiatives in the areas of arts, culture, heritage, higher-education, and other forms of activism such as Mini-Active, an organization that encourages women to report different hazards to the municipality. Involving hundreds of women and spanning multiple neighbourhoods in East Jerusalem, they have had many success stories including getting the municipality to repair broken street lights and increasing the budget for cleaning the streets. Other examples speak to an increased sense of shared everyday life, including language exchange classes, placemaking initiatives, and youth-oriented events that involve both Israelis and Palestinians. A case in point is the Good Neighbours project in the divided neighbourhood of Abu-Tor/A-Thuri, a bottom-up initiative of Israeli and Palestinian residents interested in getting to know one another through collective activities. Such activities result from living closely in urban space and encountering one another on an ongoing basis. To be sure, Jerusalem is still a highly segregated and contested space, but there are also opportunities—albeit limited—for tolerance, if not a deeper sense of shared destiny.

A hint of this everyday perspective of the city can be found in the interviews conducted with civic leaders and activists in East Jerusalem. When we asked the

participants, 'What is your vision for Jerusalem?', we anticipated responses that would be solely related to Jerusalem's position as a religious and national centre for the Palestinian people. However, in most cases, people talked about tolerance and acceptance and living together—having “normal” lives—and about envisioning a borderless city with shared living. There may be a generational aspect to this phenomenon. Since the Oslo Agreement and the Palestinian Authority's establishment, traditional leadership strongholds in Jerusalem have been oppressed and eroded (El Kurd 2018). Younger generation Jerusalemites grew up in a vacuum of leadership and a transition from a traditional society to a more urban and secular one. The 'divide and rule' policy of the Israeli government that separates East Jerusalemites from Palestinians in the West Bank, as well as from Palestinians who are citizens of Israel, has resulted, however unintentionally, in a stronger Jerusalem-based identity. This may create in the future more of a shared city, a version of *Metrozenship* (Yiftachel 2016) that would counteract radical nationalistic trends.

In conclusion, when examined from the urban, local scale, we can see that Jerusalem is not simply a microcosm of national-level politics, but that it offers a different, more complex urban geopolitics (Rokem et al. 2017) that is shaped by everyday life and micro-geographies of encounter (Greenberg Raanan and Avni 2020; Shtern 2016). Local institutions and initiatives in East Jerusalem have managed, in an admittedly limited way, to advance a notion of urban citizenship that is grounded in everyday life and local needs. Still, East Jerusalem is under an occupation that affects all spheres of life, and its significance should not be underplayed. The urban citizenship that I am referring to here is fragile, inconsistent, and fragmented (Blokland et al. 2015; Millstein 2017), and it is not likely to be a viable alternative to exclusionary forms of national citizenship. This is especially apparent when considering that most East-Jerusalemite Palestinians are not citizens, and that their residency status is precarious. Moreover, given plans to exclude them from the future municipal boundary, the future of neighbourhoods that are currently part of the Jerusalem Municipality but on the Palestinian side of the Separation Wall remains unclear. While everyday life continues to produce opportunities for solidarity and shared struggles, it cannot fully resist growing waves of populism or the 'old' and 'new' forms of nationalism.

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